

A STUDY ON THE NEED AND BENEFIT OF VOCATIONAL PROGRAMMES AT UNDERGRADUATE LEVEL – BRIDGING GAP BETWEEN STUDENTS AND WORKPLACE – A STUDENTS PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

In the present era the students want to earn just after the completion of their basic education, so there is a much need of professional courses that helps the students to attain this goal. Students who receive vocational education gain practical, useful skills that they can apply immediately upon graduation and throughout their program.

Through vocational education schools and programmes, there are numerous industry and career opportunities available. The National Center for Educational Statistics reports that the various sectors/domain like finance, marketing, retail, banking, insurance, office administration, construction, and consumer services are the most sought-after professions.

Strong job markets and professional development, a wide range of possibilities for vocational programmes/courses, and investment value are the three primary categories of the advantages of a vocational education. With the equipped knowledge in the required field the student can get placed just after the completion of undergraduate programme. The course curriculum of vocational programme is designed in such a way that it acts as a bridge between the student and the industry.

This paper tries to led focus on the need and benefit of professional/vocational programmes that really helps the students in getting the job also a hand on experience that helps them in the workplace.

Keywords: *Vocational, Opportunities, Job Oriented*

INTRODUCTION

Numerous courses, degrees, and certificates are offered by institutions worldwide. Understanding the differences and what each one means is essential to your decision-making. Consider pursuing a vocational course or degree if you're searching for a career-oriented educational path that emphasizes practical skills.

A vocational course prepares students for a specific trade or skilled employment by emphasizing experiential learning. This stands in contrast to the more cerebral and theoretical courses that could lead to a variety of professions, like mathematics, philosophy, or history. The core purpose of vocational programs is to provide students with the skills necessary to enter the workforce. Vocational courses are appropriate for students who have a clear idea of their career path and wish to acquire the skills necessary to get there.

Vocational degrees and credentials have occasionally been viewed as less prestigious or desirable than other programs, such an academic or professional degree. This is untrue, though, and a lot relies on the vocational course's level. A postgraduate program or even an

undergraduate degree can be equated with some occupational courses. Compared to more conventional, academic courses, a vocational degree can be more appropriate for you if you learn best in a hands-on setting.

Vocational programs have gained policy priority in many nations in recent years. There are three primary causes. First, by equipping the workforce with trade, technical, and professional skills, vocational programs play a significant economic role. Second, there are indications of new pressures in the systems of vocational programs, such as a shortage of teachers and vocational trainers and a lack of workplace training locations. Third, historically, vocational programs have been overlooked.

These are just a few examples of vocational subjects and courses which are offered at universities and colleges around the world which are listed below:

Table: 1. Shows the number of vocational courses all around the world.

<p style="text-align: center;">Business Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accounting • Business Studies • E-Commerce • Entrepreneurship • Finance & Insurance • Human Resource • Marketing & Advertising • Retail Management • Office Administration • Banking 	<p style="text-align: center;">Travel & Hospitality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aviation • Catering • Leisure Management • Hotel Management • Travel & Tourism • Hospitality 	<p style="text-align: center;">Law</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil Law • Criminal Law • International • Legal Advice • Legal Studies
<p style="text-align: center;">Applied and Pure Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemistry • Biology • Physics • Mathematics • General Science • Bio Medical Science 	<p style="text-align: center;">Architecture and Construction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Architecture • Construction • Maintenance Service • Planning • Surveying 	<p style="text-align: center;">Engineering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil • Electronic • Electrical • Mechanical • Bio Medical • General Engineering

Humanities	Social Studies & Media	Computer Science and IT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •English Studies •History •Langauge •Archaclogy •Philosphy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Film / Television •International Relation •Photography •Economics •Public Administration •Politics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Computer Science •Computing •Multimedia •Software

Graduate and postgraduate students are produced by vocational/professional academic institutions in a variety of management, business, and scientific fields. These vocational/professional students are intended for a variety of businesses, including the finance, marketing, and management sectors as well as the service, construction, and logistics sectors. These institutions exist primarily to produce managers and technocrats who are knowledgeable, skilled, and trained to meet the needs of various sectors. For the development of society and the nation, the invention of new technologies and their practical applications are necessary. Industries do the job of practical application very well. For adopting new technologies modernization and updatation of industries and their manpower is essential. Industries can be modernized by importing new machineries and software installation, but for updating or providing advance training to old employees as well as employing the skilled personnel the factory and industries have to depend on academic institution as a must.

The vocational/professional colleges have established a powerful board of industrial and institutional relationships, which is made up of the top figures in business, science, and technology, to assure the successful execution of these vocational programmes.

In our country, expansion in central higher vocational/professional education is taking place at very fast speed. The economic liberalization of the nineties changes the scale dramatically. A growing middle class, having mammoth population, showing education the route to a better life of their kids especially the technical and vocational/professional education. The rise in vocational/professional education is tremendous. The situation is alarming and challenging. So the implementation of these recommendations in time by the concerned agencies such as vocational/professional department of colleges, colleges, universities, industries, the government and other is highly necessitated for a sustainable growth of the nation.

Vocational Programmes: Bridging the gap between students and workplace

The gap between learning and work is significant for many companies and learners in vocational education and training. Learning is frequently viewed as academic, abstract, and classroom-based. The working world is viewed as being made of concrete, with employers and clients, revenue and equipment. Those are stereotypes, yes, but there is some truth to them. Institutions that offer vocational programmes have a style and attitude that is very distinct from the working world, as well as institutional aims, financing incentives, and limits that are all unique. Nevertheless, despite the division, vocational programme institutions' role still consists of

offering learning that will prepare students for the workforce. Different nations are attempting to achieve this. they are forming alliances with businesses to secure the provision of vocational programmes.

Vocational Programmes: Value based education

Speakers were emphatic during the deliberations that spiritual, ethical and moral values including nurturing commitments to human & social value are the main aspect of imparting all forms of education including technical and vocational/professional education.

Vocational Programmes: Soft skills

Interpersonal and communication skills, Leadership traits, Intercultural and cultural empathy, Analytical ability, Effective communication and problem solving, Creative innovation, Exposure to entrepreneurship development programme

Competence Profile of Tomorrow's Managers

Hard skill consisting of fundamental commercial knowledge complemented by knowledge from neighboring vocational/professional disciplines with some broad on job training exposure gained through field experience.

Benefits of Vocational Education

The advantages of vocational education are innumerable. All of them acquire a variety of life skills that will be beneficial to them in the future. By utilizing their abilities in life, people make the most of their time and live happy lives. They learn new things about life. The core benefit of vocational education is Higher Earnings: Earnings with this level of schooling will be higher. Earnings rise as a result of postsecondary education. Industries in the business, technology, and health sectors increase profits the greatest. Secondly, is the Increase Job Satisfaction: When they take the proper lessons and receive the necessary training, those peoples are happier. They might become more at ease and confident when searching for jobs after receiving training. Their mental capacity increases. They are more assured when applying for job requirements.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Grubb, 2006 Even while the term "vocational programs" refers to a certain kind of education and training, different countries have different definitions of what vocational programs are and how they are implemented. The definitions and status of vocational programs, the balance between academic and practical content, whether vocational programs are offered at work or in an institution, the kind of training required or delivered, and the flexibility of programs to meet market demands are some of the issues that different countries handle differently.

Based on 61st round of NSSO survey (2004–2005), only 4% of the population between 15 and 29 years had received (or was receiving at the time of survey) formal vocational education & training (Vocational Education Training) and 8% of that age group had received non-formal Vocational Education Training. A vast majority of the population (89%) in that age group do not have any sort of Vocational Education Training.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To know about the benefits and need of vocational programs which help the students to connect themselves in different workplaces.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

As the present study is an attempt to find out the benefit and need of vocational programmes that really helps the undergraduate students to get their job in the desired field/sector. The investigators adopt the normative survey method for the present study. The sample for the present study was collected from various institutions of Ranchi where the vocational programs were conducted. The sample includes students pursuing their undergraduate courses.

The major tools for the present study are Observation Schedule, Questionnaire for students. Qualitative analysis was employed for analysis of data obtained through the observation schedule and interview schedule.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

After collecting all the data from the source, the data were systematically arranged and tabulated for analysis and interpretation in a spreadsheet. Since the respondents were students who were pursuing their undergraduate program, and mostly the students were from the traditional course.

Fig 1. Age of the Respondents

Interpretation: The above pie chart depicts the age of the respondents; the majority of the respondents fall in the age group between 18-21 years, followed by 22-25 years, and 26- 30 years.

Fig 2. Gender of the Respondents

Interpretation: The above pie chart depicts the gender of the respondents; the majority of the respondents are female i.e. girls students, followed male i.e. boys students.

Fig 3. Level of the Study of the Respondents

Interpretation: The above pie chart depicts the level of study of the respondents; the majority

Fig 4. Respondent's opinion, how important are vocational programmes in preparing students for the workforce?

of the respondents are in their second year of the study, followed third and fourth year.

Interpretation: The above pie chart depicts how important vocational programmes/courses are, which help them in preparing them for their workforce. The majority say it is very important, which helps them to connect them in the workforce. 67% says it is very important which can connect to the real workforce followed by 30%, 2% and so on.

Fig 5. Field of Study of the Respondents

Interpretation: The above graph depicts the field of the study that the respondents are going through. The majority of students are from science background who think that vocational programmes/courses in undergraduate really connect to the practical job oriented world, followed by students of arts and humanities, business/management, social science and others.

Fig 6. Represents the skills of the respondents are lacking in traditional academic programmes.

Interpretation: The above graph shows that the skills of the respondents are lacking in traditional academic programmes. Majority of the respondents feels that real world practical experience/exposures are lacking in the traditional courses followed by technical skills, communication skills, leadership and teamwork, problem solving skills, time management along with the digital literacy.

The traditional courses/programmes are more focused on the curriculum whereas the vocational programmes are focused on both which help to prepare the students for the real world/job oriented. In the vocational programmes/courses the students are prepared to perform in the real stage which help them to provide ample of opportunity just after the study. Activities like internship, on the job training, industry visit, seminar and workshop from the industry expert which gives hand on experience and add value in the professional career.

Fig 7. Respondent's understanding regarding vocational programmes.

Interpretation: Many of the respondents feels that the add on of vocational programmes through NEP gives wide range of diversification in the career. Like many of the respondents says that selection of minor course along with the major course gives diversification and build interest and helps in choosing best path for their career. For example, if they the students of science or Arts they have an option to study the vocational course like digital marketing, event management, advertising, retail management, library science, stock market operation, banking and insurance and many more, which can add more value when they choose their career or design a goal for the future.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

According to the National Policy of Education, vocational courses will be a separate stream designed to educate students for specific jobs that span a variety of activity areas. These courses will have the following goals:

1. To offer a variety of learning possibilities.
2. To lessen the discrepancy between the supply and demand for skilled labor.

3. To give individuals seeking higher education an alternate kind of instruction. The current study examines the extent to which the goals of vocational education have been met in various regions of India and makes recommendations for improvements to the current system of vocational higher secondary education.

The necessity of establishing a connection between the fields of education and employment was highlighted by the National Curriculum Framework. Its objective was to instill a favorable attitude toward labor from an early age. To achieve this, organized, carefully thought out, and strictly implemented vocational education programs must be introduced. The current study examines this goal in terms of the connection that vocational education has made with the possible workplace.

Investigating the logistics of offering vocational courses in terms of pass-out certification, equivalency with other courses of a similar kind, employer recruitment on campus, and the upkeep of placement records at each institution is the goal of the current study. The current study addresses this issue, which will allow the authorities to make adjustments when creating different vocational programs in order to better meet the problems of the future.

CONCLUSION

A fantastic approach for students to receive an education that will prepare them for a certain career in the future is through vocational degrees. Due to the fact that they are not considered to be typical academic disciplines, these kinds of education are occasionally denigrated. On the other hand, they are essential in ensuring that the workforce is diverse and that every sector has the specialists it requires to thrive.

The prospects of struggling students may be saved by a vocational degree, particularly if they have a learning style that suits them. Vocational education offers so many degrees and career options that many people find it to be a very alluring idea. Consider a vocational degree if you or someone you know is unsure about their next educational step, particularly if you know the field you want to work in.

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